

FEATURES OF STENTING IN PATIENTS WITH MALIGNANT STENOSIS

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Relevance: Dysphagia is a common problem. One in 17 people will develop some form of dysphagia during their lifetime. A 2011 UK study shows a prevalence of dysphagia of 11% in the general population [9]. The condition develops in 40–70% of patients with stroke, 60–80% of patients with neurodegenerative diseases, nearly 13% of adults aged 65 and older, and >51% of elderly patients in nursing homes [10,11]. It also affects 60–75% of patients receiving radiotherapy for head and neck cancer.

Purpose of the study: to study the features of stenting of patients with malignant stenosis.

Materials and methods of research: The basis for this scientific study was the experience of treating 390 patients with dysphagia syndrome caused by various malignant diseases of the esophagus. All patients were hospitalized at the Department of Surgery of the Esophagus and Stomach of the State Institution "Republican Specialized Center for Surgery named after N.N. acad. V. Vakhidov" for the period from 2000 to 2021

Conclusions:

1. thus, the main point of using stenting is the possibility of oral nutrition, because. Tunnelization and bougienage cannot provide long-term restoration of esophageal patency due to the constant growth of the tumor, again obturating the lumen.

2. The stent limits the stenosis of the tumor lumen, acting as a scaffold. However, stenting cannot be used in all patients, because two conditions are necessary: the presence of suprastenotic expansion and a circular lesion in order to prevent stent migration.

When evaluating the immediate results of stenting, it was found that, in the control group, out of 241 patients who used stents of their own design, no complications were noted in 188 patients, which amounted to 78%. In the main group, out of 149 patients who used self-expanding nitinol stents, no complications were observed in 144 patients, which amounted to 96.6%.

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